

released on 40-d-old potted TN1 plants. After 24 h of infestation, the insects were removed and half the potted plants containing eggs were submerged in a 44°C hot water bath. The remaining half were submerged in ordinary

tap water. Nymphs that hatched from all potted plants were counted 11 d after infestation.

Dipping the plants in hot water for 30 min caused 99% mortality of BPH and WBPH eggs (see figure) and had no

adverse effect on the rice plants. Mortality of *C. lividipennis* eggs was 88%, but mortality of GLH eggs was only 63%. We are now using this technique for BPH rearing. □

Deepwater rice and yellow stem borer (YSB) larvae

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There is relatively little information on the anatomy of elongated deepwater rice plants. We studied plant anatomy and the effect of YSB *Scirpophaga incertulas* (Walker) feeding on rice yield.

Cut ends of elongated Chamara stems were immersed in an aniline blue dye solution for 2-3 d and then examined for YSB larvae infestation. Stems were dissected longitudinally or sectioned to study the effect of larval feeding. Vascular tissue was stained blue and photographs and drawings were made of the damage (see figure).

The nodal septum is of undifferentiated tissue (no vascular tissue); therefore, larval passage through the septum did not disrupt conduction or reduce growth above an infested internode. Feeding in the internodes seldom penetrated into the parenchyma as far as the inner ring of vascular bundles, and even then conduction was disrupted in only few vascular bundles. At the node, vascular tissue forms a dense continuous ring that connects the incoming bundles from the internode. Although we found larvae actively feeding in the

Internal structure of a basal tiller of an elongated deepwater rice plant: a) longitudinal section of 5th node from the top; b) tissue section of 4th internode from the top.

fourth or fifth internode below the stem growing point, there was never an obvious interruption of xylem flow to the apex. Even if the larva was feeding immediately below the panicle-bearing stem, the flow to the upper xylem was not interrupted and the panicle appeared normal.

Larval damage early in the season, where internode tissue at the base of the plant was severely damaged, caused the plant to produce aquatic roots and

tolerate YSB. In one or two instances, deadhearts were caused by small first- or second-instar larvae that had bored between the flag leaf sheath and the stem and had entered just above the top node. Larval feeding had cut a ring around the narrow apical stem, almost severing it. That interrupted the vascular system and killed the apex. Later in the season, examination of many whiteheads showed similar excision of the apical stem. □

Incidence of gall midge (GM) *Orseolia oryzivora* H & G in Edozhigi, Nigeria

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In Africa, GM occurs in the Sudan, Cameroon, Mali, Upper Volta, Ivory

Coast, Senegal, Guinea Bissau, and Nigeria. Except in Upper Volta, it is considered as a localized pest. In Upper Volta, GM is one of the most serious and widespread pests on irrigated and rainfed lowland rice. The African GM species is morphologically distinct from the Asian species *O. oryzae*.

In Nigeria, GM is found in Gwangum (Plateau State) and Badeggi (Niger State). GM incidence is increasing at Edozhigi,

a research farm for irrigated rice of the NCRI. Rice crops planted after mid-Oct often are seriously-affected. GM was also observed on farmer plots in Agaie and Jima in 1982 and 1983.

The 8th International Rice Gall Midge Nursery (90 entries) was planted at Edozhigi in 1982. Infestation was 0.5 to 23.6%. Only 6 entries, BW100, 0B677, Eswarakora, Cisdane, Ptb 10, and WGL 22397, had less than 2% infestation. □